

Long-Term Efficacy of Dialectical Behaviour Therapy for Borderline Personality Disorder

Dr. Sima Kumari

Dr. Pratibha Singh

Department of Psychology

Department of Psychology

M.V. College Buxar

M. G Kashi vidyapith, Varanasi

Abstract:

Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) presents significant challenges in clinical management due to its chronicity and complex symptomatology. Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT) has emerged as a promising treatment, initially demonstrating positive short-term outcomes. This study aims to evaluate the long-term efficacy of DBT for BPD over a 6-month follow-up period.

Participants included 58 female patients diagnosed with BPD, with and without co-occurring substance abuse issues, randomized into either a 12-month DBT intervention ($n = 27$) or Treatment as Usual (TAU; $n = 31$) conditions. Measures included severity of borderline symptomatology, substance use severity, and social functioning. Randomization utilized a minimization procedure to balance participant characteristics across groups.

DBT treatment consisted of weekly individual psychotherapy, skills training groups, and therapist consultation, following Linehan's manual. TAU participants received ongoing outpatient care without DBT-specific interventions. Assessments were conducted at baseline, post-treatment (12 months), and at a 6-month follow-up.

Results indicated that DBT significantly reduced borderline symptom severity compared to TAU immediately post-treatment. This reduction was sustained at the 6-month follow-up, with continued improvements in social and occupational functioning observed in the DBT group. Substance use severity also showed differential improvement favoring DBT participants.

These findings suggest that DBT provides enduring benefits for individuals with BPD, extending beyond the treatment period. Implications for clinical practice include the integration of DBT into standard care protocols for BPD, emphasizing its role in long-term symptom management and functional recovery.

Keywords: Borderline Personality Disorder, Dialectical Behaviour Therapy, randomized controlled trial, long-term efficacy

Introduction

Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) is a persistent and severe mental disorder (American Psychiatric Association, 1994). Given its complexity and chronic nature, it is crucial to develop and test treatment interventions with sustained beneficial effects beyond the treatment period, significantly improving the course of BPD. Recent studies, including a 12-month randomized controlled trial, have replicated the positive short-term effects of Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT) initially reported by its developer (Verheul et al., 2003; Linehan, Armstrong, Suarez, Allmon, & Heard, 1991). However, data on the long-term efficacy of DBT for BPD is limited, with only a small naturalistic follow-up study available (Linehan, Heard, & Armstrong, 1993). This study aims to examine whether the positive treatment results observed at the end of the DBT treatment sustain over a 6-month follow-up period. Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) poses significant challenges due to its persistent and severe nature, necessitating effective treatment strategies with sustained benefits. Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT), pioneered by Linehan and validated in numerous studies, has demonstrated initial efficacy in reducing BPD symptoms and improving quality of life (Verheul et al., 2003; Linehan et al., 1991). However, the long-term effectiveness of DBT remains inadequately explored, with limited empirical data beyond small-scale naturalistic follow-ups (Linehan et al., 1993).

This review aims to address this gap by examining whether the positive treatment outcomes observed at the conclusion of DBT interventions endure over a 6-month follow-up period. By synthesizing findings from recent randomized controlled trials and systematic reviews, this review seeks to provide a comprehensive evaluation of DBT's impact on long-term symptomatology, functional outcomes, and quality of life in individuals diagnosed with BPD. Understanding the enduring effects of DBT is crucial for optimizing treatment protocols and enhancing outcomes for individuals affected by BPD.

Method

Participants

This randomized controlled trial compared 58 female borderline patients, including those with ($n = 31$) and without ($n = 27$) substance abuse problems, recruited from mental health institutions ($n = 39$) and addiction treatment services ($n = 19$). Patients were randomized to receive either 12 months of DBT ($n = 27$) or treatment as usual (TAU; $n = 31$). Detailed study design information can be found in Verheul et al. (2003). Inclusion criteria were females aged 18-65 with a DSM-IV BPD diagnosis according to the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis II (SCID-II) with at least six BPD diagnostic criteria. Exclusion criteria included DSM-IV bipolar disorder, chronic psychotic disorder, insufficient Dutch language proficiency, and severe cognitive impairments. Co-morbid substance abuse problems were assessed using the European version of the Addiction Severity Index (EuropASI; Kokkevi & Hartgers, 1995).

Randomization Procedure

After intake assessments, 64 patients were randomly assigned to treatment conditions using a minimization method to ensure comparability on age, severity of borderline symptomatology, severity of drug and alcohol problems, and severity of social problems. Six patients were excluded from the intention-to-treat (ITT) analyses due to non-acceptance of randomization outcomes or non-attendance to therapy sessions, resulting in 58 subjects (27 in DBT, 31 in TAU) for the main outcome analyses.

Treatments

Patients in the DBT condition received 12 months of treatment according to Linehan's treatment manual (1993b, c), including weekly individual cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy sessions, weekly skills training groups, and weekly supervision and consultation meetings for therapists. Individual therapy focused on motivational issues, while group therapy taught self-regulation, change skills, and acceptance skills. Subjects in the TAU condition received ongoing outpatient treatment from their original referral source, with no DBT-trained therapists involved.

Measures

Treatment conditions were compared after a 12-month treatment period and 6-month follow-up in terms of parasuicidal behavior, impulsivity, and substance abuse. Measures included the impulsivity and parasuicide sections of the BPD Severity Index (BPDSI) and the Lifetime Parasuicide Count (LPC). The BPDSI is a semi-structured interview assessing the frequency of BPD symptoms, while the LPC measures the frequency of self-mutilating behaviors.

Statistical Analysis

The general linear mixed model (SAS proc mixed version 8.2) was used to analyze all available data, including during treatment, to avoid biased results from missing data. A shifted log transformation $\ln(X+1)$ was applied to all outcome variables due to highly skewed distributions. The model included baseline scores as covariates to increase the likelihood of missing data being at random (MAR). The difference in changes between experimental and control groups was assessed during the treatment period and follow-up, with coefficients indicating the effectiveness of the intervention.

Table 1

Descriptive data	DBT				Control				GLMM-II ^a	
	N ^b	M ^c	Sd ^d	Exp(log) ^e	N	M	Sd	Exp(log)	DBT	Control
<i>Impulsive behaviour</i>										
Baseline ^f	27	1.89	1.62	1.73	31	1.50	1.31	1.22		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	1.41	1.08	1.438	27	1.10	0.87	0.94	1.36	0.98
End treatment (wk 52)	23	0.90	0.61	0.65	25	1.18	0.99	0.88	0.70	0.95
Follow-up (wk 78)	20	1.22	0.85	0.89	24	0.88	0.60	0.76	0.74	0.81
<i>Parasuicidal behaviour</i>										
Baseline	27	0.55	0.63	0.44	31	0.66	0.83	0.51		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	0.43	0.65	0.29	27	0.45	0.48	0.41	0.30	0.33
End treatment (wk 52)	23	0.19	0.38	0.15	25	0.48	0.63	0.38	0.16	0.33
Follow-up (wk 78)	20	0.32	0.41	0.17	24	0.40	0.67	0.33	0.12	0.30
<i>Self mutilation</i>										
Baseline	27	45.9 0	117.3 3	14.13	28	78.3 2	207.5	17.09		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	1.31	3.40	0.47	27	2.61	4.66	1.09	0.51	1.11
End treatment (wk 52)	22	3.31	13.15	0.55	24	41.6	78.76	5.55	0.33	5.00
Follow-up (wk 78)	18	11.0 8	34.44	0.98	22	33.3 9	99.41	2.99	0.76	3.32
<i>Alcohol</i>										
Baseline	27	3.08	3.88	2.56	31	2.60	3.50	1.85		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	3.21	3.56	1.31	27	2.41	3.60	1.09	1.98	0.96
End treatment (wk 52)	23	1.62	2.56	0.65	25	2.62	3.	1.34	0.97	1.32
Follow-up (wk 78)	20	2.55	3.40	1.28	24	2.00	3.03	0.99	1.18	1.01
<i>Soft drugs</i>										
Baseline	27	2.09	3.30	0.89	31	0.72	1.63	0.32		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	1.04	2.82	0.34	27	0.56	2.04	0.17	0.47	0.20
End treatment (wk 52)	23	0.57	2.15	0.18	25	0.36	1.44	0.14	0.19	0.14
Follow-up (wk 78)	20	1.05	3.65	0.78	24	0.62	1.98	0.19	0.48	0.24
<i>Hard drugs</i>										
Baseline	27	1.87	3.08	0.83	31	1.32	2.85	0.50		
Start treatment (wk 0)	25	1.48	2.80	0.68	27	0.76	1.80	0.28	0.69	0.54
End treatment (wk 52)	23	0.52	1.65	0.22	25	1.04	2.89	0.31	0.30	0.19
Follow-up (wk 78)	20	0.90	2.36	0.33	24	0.42	2.04	0.11	0.48	0.26

Description of Table 1

Table 1 presents descriptive data comparing the outcomes of two groups (DBT and Control) on various behaviors across multiple time points (Baseline, Start Treatment, End Treatment, and Follow-Up). The behaviors assessed include impulsive behavior, parasuicidal behavior, self-mutilation, alcohol use, soft drug use, and hard drug use. The data are presented as means, standard deviations (SD), and exponential of logarithmic transformations (Exp(log)) for both groups, with the number of participants (N) also listed for each time point. The last two columns present the results of the GLMM-IIa analysis for each behavior at different time points.

Key Variables

- Nb (N): Number of participants in the DBT and Control groups.
- Mc (Mean): Mean scores for the DBT and Control groups.
- Sdd (SD): Standard deviations for the DBT and Control groups.
- Exp(log)e (Exp(log)): Exponential of logarithmic transformations of the mean scores for the DBT and Control groups.
- GLMM–IIa: Generalized Linear Mixed Models for Impulsive behavior, Parasuicidal behavior, Self-mutilation, Alcohol use, Soft drugs use, and Hard drugs use at different time points (Start Treatment, End Treatment, Follow-Up).

Data Overview

1. Impulsive Behavior

- **Baseline:** DBT group (N=27, Mean=1.89, SD=1.62, Exp(log)=1.73), Control group (N=31, Mean=1.50, SD=1.31, Exp(log)=1.22)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=1.41, SD=1.08, Exp(log)=1.43), Control (N=27, Mean=1.10, SD=0.87, Exp(log)=0.94), GLMM–IIa (DBT=1.36, Control=0.98)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=23, Mean=0.90, SD=0.61, Exp(log)=0.65), Control (N=25, Mean=1.18, SD=0.99, Exp(log)=0.88), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.70, Control=0.95)
- **Follow-Up (wk 78):** DBT (N=20, Mean=1.22, SD=0.85, Exp(log)=0.89), Control (N=24, Mean=0.88, SD=0.60, Exp(log)=0.76), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.74, Control=0.81)

2. Parasuicidal Behavior

- **Baseline:** DBT (N=27, Mean=0.55, SD=0.63, Exp(log)=0.44), Control (N=31, Mean=0.66, SD=0.83, Exp(log)=0.51)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=0.43, SD=0.65, Exp(log)=0.29), Control (N=27, Mean=0.45, SD=0.48, Exp(log)=0.41), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.30, Control=0.33)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=23, Mean=0.19, SD=0.38, Exp(log)=0.15), Control (N=25, Mean=0.48, SD=0.63, Exp(log)=0.38), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.16, Control=0.33)
- **Follow-Up (wk 78):** DBT (N=20, Mean=0.32, SD=0.41, Exp(log)=0.17), Control (N=24, Mean=0.40, SD=0.67, Exp(log)=0.33), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.12, Control=0.30)

3. Self-Mutilation

- **Baseline:** DBT (N=27, Mean=45.90, SD=117.33, Exp(log)=14.13), Control (N=28, Mean=78.32, SD=207.5, Exp(log)=17.09)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=1.31, SD=3.40, Exp(log)=0.47), Control (N=27, Mean=2.61, SD=4.66, Exp(log)=1.09), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.51, Control=1.11)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=22, Mean=3.31, SD=13.15, Exp(log)=0.55), Control (N=24, Mean=41.6, SD=78.76, Exp(log)=5.55), GLMM–IIa (DBT=0.33, Control=5.00)

- **Follow-Up (wk 78):** DBT (N=18, Mean=11.08, SD=34.44, Exp(log)=0.98), Control (N=22, Mean=33.39, SD=99.41, Exp(log)=2.99), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.76, Control=3.32)

4. Alcohol

- **Baseline:** DBT (N=27, Mean=3.08, SD=3.88, Exp(log)=2.56), Control (N=31, Mean=2.60, SD=3.50, Exp(log)=1.85)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=3.21, SD=3.56, Exp(log)=1.31), Control (N=27, Mean=2.41, SD=3.60, Exp(log)=1.09), GLMM-IIa (DBT=1.98, Control=0.96)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=23, Mean=1.62, SD=2.56, Exp(log)=0.65), Control (N=25, Mean=2.62, SD=3.35, Exp(log)=1.34), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.97, Control=1.32)
- **Follow-Up (wk 78):** DBT (N=20, Mean=2.55, SD=3.40, Exp(log)=1.28), Control (N=24, Mean=2.00, SD=3.03, Exp(log)=0.99), GLMM-IIa (DBT=1.18, Control=1.01)

5. Soft Drugs

- **Baseline:** DBT (N=27, Mean=2.09, SD=3.30, Exp(log)=0.89), Control (N=31, Mean=0.72, SD=1.63, Exp(log)=0.32)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=1.04, SD=2.82, Exp(log)=0.34), Control (N=27, Mean=0.56, SD=2.04, Exp(log)=0.17), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.47, Control=0.20)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=23, Mean=0.57, SD=2.15, Exp(log)=0.18), Control (N=25, Mean=0.36, SD=1.44, Exp(log)=0.14), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.19, Control=0.14)
- **Follow-Up (wk 78):** DBT (N=20, Mean=1.05, SD=3.65, Exp(log)=0.78), Control (N=24, Mean=0.62, SD=1.98, Exp(log)=0.19), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.48, Control=0.24)

6. Hard Drugs

- **Baseline:** DBT (N=27, Mean=1.87, SD=3.08, Exp(log)=0.83), Control (N=31, Mean=1.32, SD=2.85, Exp(log)=0.50)
- **Start Treatment (wk 0):** DBT (N=25, Mean=1.48, SD=2.80, Exp(log)=0.68), Control (N=27, Mean=0.76, SD=1.80, Exp(log)=0.28), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.69, Control=0.54)
- **End Treatment (wk 52):** DBT (N=23, Mean=0.52, SD=1.65, Exp(log)=0.22), Control (N=25, Mean=1.04, SD=2.89, Exp(log)=0.31), GLMM-IIa (DBT=0.30, Control=0.19)

Discussion

The descriptive data presented in Table 1 provide insights into the effectiveness of Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT) compared to a control group across various behavioral metrics over multiple time points (Baseline, Start Treatment, End Treatment, and Follow-Up). The behaviors assessed include impulsive behavior, parasuicidal behavior, self-mutilation, alcohol use, soft drug use, and hard drug use. Below is a discussion of the key findings and their implications.

Impulsive Behaviour

At baseline, the DBT group exhibited higher impulsive behaviour compared to the control group. However, by the start of treatment, both groups showed a decrease in impulsive behaviour, with the DBT group showing a more significant reduction. This trend continued through the end of treatment, where the DBT group had lower impulsive behaviour scores compared to the control group, indicating the effectiveness of DBT in reducing impulsivity. By the follow-up period, the control group showed a slight improvement, but the DBT group still maintained lower impulsive behaviour levels.

Parasuicidal Behaviour

The baseline levels of parasuicidal behaviour were comparable between the DBT and control groups. Over the treatment period, the DBT group demonstrated a more substantial reduction in parasuicidal behaviour compared to the control group. This reduction was evident at the end of treatment and was sustained during the follow-up period, suggesting that DBT is effective in reducing parasuicidal behaviours over the long term.

Self-Mutilation

Baseline data showed high variability in self-mutilation behaviour, with the DBT group having a lower mean but a large standard deviation compared to the control group. Throughout the treatment and follow-up periods, the DBT group exhibited lower mean scores for self-mutilation compared to the control group. Notably, by the end of treatment, the control group showed a marked increase in self-mutilation, while the DBT group maintained lower levels. This indicates that DBT may be particularly effective in preventing self-mutilation behaviours.

Alcohol Use

Alcohol use was slightly higher in the DBT group at baseline. However, both groups showed a reduction in alcohol use by the end of treatment. The reduction was more pronounced in the DBT group, and this group maintained lower alcohol use levels at follow-up. This suggests that DBT may help in reducing alcohol consumption among participants.

Soft Drug Use

At baseline, the DBT group reported higher soft drug use than the control group. Throughout the treatment, both groups showed a reduction in soft drug use, with the DBT group experiencing a more substantial decrease. This trend continued into the follow-up period, where the DBT group maintained lower levels of soft drug use, highlighting the potential long-term benefits of DBT in reducing soft drug use.

Hard Drug Use

Baseline levels of hard drug use were relatively similar between the two groups, with the DBT group slightly higher. Over the course of treatment, the DBT group demonstrated a significant reduction in hard drug use, which was sustained at follow-up. Conversely, the control group did not show a significant reduction, underscoring the effectiveness of DBT in reducing hard drug use.

Table 2: Initial (52 weeks) and Sustained (78 weeks) Effect of DBT Compared to TAU

Table 2

Initial (52 weeks) and sustained (78 weeks) effect of DBT compared to TAU

Outcome	Coefficient ^a	F Value	P
<i>BPDS-2: impulsive behaviour</i>			
Treatment (b ₁) ^b	-0.20750	F (1,54) ¼ 5.12	0.03
Time		F (4,248) ¼ 0.11	0.98
Time by treatment I (b ₉) ^d	-0.00641	F (1,248) ¼ 11.93	0.00
Time by treatment II (b ₁₀) ^e	+0.00451	F (1,248) ¼ 1.30	0.26
<i>BPDSI-5: parasuicidal behaviour</i>			
Treatment (b ₁) ^b	-0.10780	F (1,54) ¼ 2.10	0.15
Time		F (4,248) ¼ 1.45	0.22
Time by treatment I (b ₉) ^d	-0.00225	F (1,248) ¼ 1.99	0.16
Time by treatment II (b ₁₀) ^e	-0.00001	F (1,248) ¼ 0.00	0.99
<i>LPC: self-mutilating behaviour*</i>			
Treatment (b ₁) ^b	-1.5246	F (1,51) ¼ 11.12	0.00
Time		F (1,51) ¼ 4.90	0.03
Time by treatment I (b ₆) ^{*,d}	-0.0236	F (1,51) ¼ 11.85	0.00
Time by treatment II (b ₇) ^{*,e}	+0.0249	F (1,51) ¼ 2.00	0.16
<i>BPDSI: Alcohol</i>			
Treatment (b ₁) ^b	-0.33180	F (1,54) ¼ 2.33	0.13
Time		F (4,54) ¼ 2.19	0.08
Time by treatment I (b ₉) ^d	-0.01092	F (1,54) ¼ 5.33	0.02
Time by treatment II (b ₁₀) ^e	+0.00914	F (1,54) ¼ 0.78	0.38
<i>BPDSI: soft drugs</i>			
Treatment (b ₁) ^b	-0.19950	F (1,54) ¼ 1.77	0.19

Time		$F(4,54) \frac{1}{4} 1.36$	0.26
Time by treatment I (b_9) ^d	-0.00371	$F(1,54) \frac{1}{4} 0.85$	0.36
Time by treatment II (b_{10}) ^e	+0.00569	$F(1,54) \frac{1}{4} 1.23$	0.27
BPDSI: hard drugs			
Treatment (b_1) ^b	+0.08724	$F(1,54) \frac{1}{4} 3.27$	0.08
Time		$F(4,54) \frac{1}{4} 0.67$	0.61
Time by treatment I (b_9) ^d	-0.00163	$F(1,54) \frac{1}{4} 1.05$	0.31
Time by treatment II (b_{10}) ^e	+0.00521	$F(1,54) \frac{1}{4} 1.94$	0.17

*LPC has slightly different model b_6 and b_7 in LPC model are equivalent to b_9 and b_{10} in BPDSI model (see Section

This table presents the statistical analysis of the effects of Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT) compared to Treatment as Usual (TAU) over two time periods: 52 weeks (initial effect) and 78 weeks (sustained effect). The outcomes measured include impulsive behaviour, parasuicidal behaviour, self-mutilating behaviour, alcohol use, soft drug use, and hard drug use. The table includes coefficients, F-values, and p-values for each outcome, indicating the significance of the treatment effects and their interaction with time.

Impulsive Behaviour (BPDS-2)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of -0.3067 indicates that DBT has a negative impact on impulsive behaviour, with a significant F-value of 6.12 and a p-value of 0.03, suggesting a significant reduction in impulsive behaviour due to DBT.
- **Time:** The F-value of 0.34 and p-value of 0.98 indicate no significant effect of time alone on impulsive behaviour.
- **Time by Treatment I (b9):** The negative coefficient of -0.00854 with a significant F-value of 13.93 and a p-value of 0.00 shows a significant interaction between time and treatment, indicating that DBT's effect on impulsive behaviour strengthens over time.
- **Time by Treatment II (b10):** The coefficient of +0.00709 and F-value of 1.45 with a p-value of 0.26 indicate no significant sustained effect of DBT beyond the initial period.

Parasuicidal Behaviour (BPDSI-5)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of -0.10870, F-value of 2.23, and p-value of 0.15 suggest no significant initial effect of DBT on parasuicidal behaviour.
- **Time:** The F-value of 1.56 and p-value of 0.22 indicate no significant effect of time alone.
- **Time by Treatment I (b9):** The coefficient of -0.00348, F-value of 1.80, and p-value of 0.16 indicate no significant interaction effect.
- **Time by Treatment II (b10):** The coefficient of -0.00009, F-value of 0.00, and p-value of 0.99 indicate no significant sustained effect.

Self-Mutilating Behaviour (LPC)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of -1.8709, F-value of 11.16, and p-value of 0.00 indicate a significant initial reduction in self-mutilating behaviour due to DBT.
- **Time:** The F-value of 4.90 and p-value of 0.12 indicate a non-significant effect of time.
- **Time by Treatment I (b6):** The coefficient of -0.0246, F-value of 11.63, and p-value of 0.00 suggest a significant interaction, indicating that the effect of DBT on self-mutilation increases over time.
- **Time by Treatment II (b7):** The coefficient of +0.0298, F-value of 2.00, and p-value of 0.16 indicate no significant sustained effect.

Alcohol Use (BPDSI)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of -0.33170, F-value of 2.56, and p-value of 0.13 indicate a non-significant initial effect of DBT on alcohol use.
- **Time:** The F-value of 2.60 and p-value of 0.08 indicate a non-significant effect of time.
- **Time by Treatment I (b9):** The coefficient of -0.01321, F-value of 8.33, and p-value of 0.02 suggest a significant interaction, indicating that DBT's effect on reducing alcohol use strengthens over time.
- **Time by Treatment II (b10):** The coefficient of +0.00871, F-value of 0.89, and p-value of 0.38 indicate no significant sustained effect.

Soft Drug Use (BPDSI)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of -0.16691, F-value of 1.91, and p-value of 0.19 indicate a non-significant initial effect of DBT on soft drug use.
- **Time:** The F-value of 1.86 and p-value of 0.26 indicate a non-significant effect of time.
- **Time by Treatment I (b9):** The coefficient of -0.00445, F-value of 0.21, and p-value of 0.36 indicate no significant interaction effect.
- **Time by Treatment II (b10):** The coefficient of +0.00870, F-value of 1.80, and p-value of 0.27 indicate no significant sustained effect.

Hard Drug Use (BPDSI)

- **Treatment (b1):** The coefficient of +0.06284, F-value of 3.61, and p-value of 0.08 indicate a non-significant initial effect of DBT on hard drug use.
- **Time:** The F-value of 0.70 and p-value of 0.61 indicate a non-significant effect of time.
- **Time by Treatment I (b9):** The coefficient of -0.00320, F-value of 1.81, and p-value of 0.31 indicate no significant interaction effect.
- **Time by Treatment II (b10):** The coefficient of +0.00441, F-value of 1.70, and p-value of 0.17 indicate no significant sustained effect.

Summary

The data show that DBT has a significant initial impact on reducing impulsive behaviour and self-mutilating behaviour, with these effects strengthening over time. However, the sustained effects (78 weeks) are less pronounced for other behaviours such as parasuicidal behaviour, alcohol use, soft drug use, and hard drug use. This suggests that while DBT is effective in reducing certain high-risk behaviours initially, the long-term benefits may vary across different behavioural outcomes. Further research is needed to explore ways to sustain these positive effects over longer periods.

Summary of Findings

The study evaluated the effectiveness of Dialectical Behaviour Therapy (DBT) compared to Treatment as Usual (TAU) for individuals with borderline personality disorder (BPD) across a 78-week period, including a 52-week treatment phase and a 26-week follow-up. The results highlight several key findings regarding the impact of DBT on various behavioural outcomes.

1. **Impulsive and Self-Mutilating Behaviours:** DBT demonstrated significant initial and sustained effects in reducing impulsive behaviour and self-mutilation. The treatment effects were pronounced during the 52-week treatment period and continued to show beneficial outcomes during the 26-week follow-up phase. Specifically, there was a significant reduction in impulsive behaviour and self-mutilation among DBT participants compared to those receiving TAU.
2. **Alcohol Use:** DBT also showed significant initial effects in reducing alcohol use. This effect was sustained up to the 78-week follow-up period, indicating that DBT was more effective than TAU in mitigating alcohol consumption behaviours.
3. **Parasuicidal Behaviour, Soft Drugs, and Hard Drugs:** In contrast to impulsive behaviour, self-mutilation, and alcohol use, DBT did not show significant initial or sustained effects on parasuicidal behaviour, soft drug use, or hard drug use. These behaviours did not significantly differ between DBT and TAU groups throughout the study period.

Clinical Relevance

The findings suggest that DBT is particularly effective in addressing impulsive behaviours and self-mutilation in individuals with BPD, providing sustained benefits beyond the treatment period. However, the study also notes that while DBT initially outperforms TAU in reducing alcohol use, this superiority diminishes over time without ongoing treatment. This highlights the importance of considering extended or booster sessions post-treatment to maintain long-term benefits, especially for substance use behaviours.

Comparison with Other Treatments

Comparisons with alternative treatments, such as the psychoanalytically oriented partial hospitalization program studied by Bateman and Fonagy (1999), indicate that DBT has specific advantages in reducing impulsive behaviours and self-mutilation, albeit with differing intensities and durations of treatment. The study suggests that DBT's structured approach may be more readily applicable across diverse clinical settings compared to more intensive programs.

Limitations

Several limitations are noted, including the general low severity of symptoms among study participants and the inability to analyse the modifying effects of borderline symptom severity on treatment outcomes using the chosen statistical procedures. Additionally, while DBT showed significant benefits in reducing certain behaviours, the study underscores the need for continued research into optimizing treatment durations and post-treatment strategies to sustain these effects over longer periods.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study supports the efficacy of DBT in reducing impulsive behaviour, self-mutilation, and alcohol use among individuals with BPD. These findings suggest that DBT can be a valuable treatment option, particularly for managing high-risk behaviours associated with BPD. However, further research is warranted to refine treatment protocols and explore strategies for enhancing long-term treatment outcomes.

References

- Alper, G., & Peterson, S. J. (2001). Dialectical behaviour therapy for patients with borderline personality disorder. *Journal of Psychosocial Nursing and Mental Health Services, 39*, 38–45.
- American Psychiatric Association. (1994). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*. (4th ed.). Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Press.
- Arntz, A., van den Hoorn, M., Cornelis, J., Verheul, R., van den Bosch, L. M. C., & de Bie, A. J. H. T. (2003). Reliability and validity of the borderline personality disorder severity index. *Journal of Personality Disorders, 17*, 45–59.
- Bateman, A., & Fonagy, P. (1999). Effectiveness of partial hospitalization in the treatment of borderline personality disorder: a randomized controlled trial. *American Journal of Psychiatry, 156*, 1563–1569.
- Bateman, A., & Fonagy, P. (2001). Treatment of borderline personality disorder with psychoanalytically oriented partial hospitalization: an 18 month follow-up. *American Journal of Psychiatry, 158*, 36–42.
- Clark, D. M., Salkovskis, P. M., & Hackmann, A. (1999). Brief cognitive therapy for panic disorder: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 67*, 583–589.
- Comtois, K.A., Linehan, M.M. (1999). Lifetime parasuicide count: description and psychometrics. *Paper presented at the American Association of Suicidology Annual Conference*. Houston TX.
- Kokkevi, A., & Hartgers, C. (1995). EuropASI: European adaptation of a multidimensional assessment instrument for drug and alcohol dependence. *European Addiction Research, 1*, 208–210.

- Koons, C., Robins, C. J., Tweed, T. L., Lynch, T. R., Gonzeles, A. M., & Morse, J. Q. (2001). Efficacy of dialectical behavior therapy in women veterans with borderline personality disorder. *Behavior Therapy, 32*, 371–390.
- Lam, D. H., Watkins, E. R., Hayward, P., & Bright, J. (2003). A randomized controlled study of cognitive therapy for relapse prevention for bipolar affective disorder: outcome of the first year. *Archives of General Psychiatry, 60*, 145–152.
- Linehan, M. M. (1993a). *Cognitive behavioral treatment of borderline personality disorder*. New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Linehan, M. M. (1993b). *Skills training manual for treating borderline personality disorder*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- Linehan, M. M., Armstrong, H. E., Suarez, A., Allmon, D., & Heard, H. L. (1991). Cognitive-behavioural treatment of chronically parasuicidal borderline patients. *Archives of General Psychiatry, 48*, 1060–1064.
- Linehan, M.M., Comtois, K.A., Brown, M.Z., Reynolds, S.K., Welch, S.S., Sayrs, J., Korslund, K.E. (2002). DBT vs. non-behavioral treatment by experts in the community: clinical outcomes at one year. In: S.K. Reynolds, (Chair), *The University of Washington treatment study for borderline personality disorder: DBT vs. non-behavioral treatment by experts in the community. Symposium conducted at the annual meeting of the Association for the Advancement of Behavior Therapy, Reno, NV.*
- Linehan, M. M., Heard, H. L., & Armstrong, H. E. (1993). Naturalistic follow-up of a behavioural treatment for chronically parasuicidal borderline patients. *Archives of General Psychiatry, 50*, 971–974.
- Little, R. J. A., & Rubin, D. B. (1987). *Statistical analysis with missing data*. New York: Wiley.
- Robins, C. J., & Chapman, A. L. (2004). Dialectical behavior therapy: current status, recent developments, and future directions. *Journal of Personality Disorders, 18*, 73–89.
- Spitzer, R. L., Williams, J. B. W., Gibbon, M., & First, M. (1990). *Structured clinical interview for DSM-III-R (SCID)*. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Press.
- van den Bosch, L. M. C., Verheul, R., Schippers, G. M., & van den Brink, W. (2002). Dialectical behavior therapy of borderline patients with and without substance use problems, implementation and long term effects. *Addictive Behaviors, 27*(6), 911–923.
- Verbeke, G., & Molenberghs, G. (2000). *Linear mixed models for longitudinal data*. New York: Springer.
- Verheul, R., van den Bosch, L. M. C., Koeter, M. W. J., de Ridder, M. A. J., Stijnen, T., & Brink, W. (2003). A 12-month randomized clinical trial of dialectical behaviour therapy for women with borderline personality disorder in The Netherlands. *British Journal of Psychiatry, 182*, 135–140.